

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INVESTIGATION OF INFLAMMATORY MARKERS IN INDIVIDUALS INFECTED WITH THE SARS-COV-2 VIRUS AND THEIR EFFECT ON COURSE

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Abstract

The coronavirus disease (SARS-CoV-2), also known as the COVID-19 pandemic, has caused acute respiratory syndrome. One of the questions that interested researchers was whether it was possible to protect against this virus with a strong immune system. In accordance with the standard protocol, clinical, etiological and laboratory data of 600 patients who underwent diagnostic tests on different dates in 2021 in Baku were collected. Symptoms of the disease were detected at the time of admission, and it was found that the most common symptoms were fatigue (81%), cough (63%), fever (57%), chest tightness or shortness of breath (32.7%). 35.7% of patients complained of gastrointestinal tract symptoms, additional nausea, diarrhea, loss of appetite, abdominal pain and vomiting. As a result of Real Time PCR analysis performed between 236 women (mean age 52.3) and 364 men (mean age 52.8), significant differences were observed in neutrophil, lymphocyte and monocyte counts.

Keywords: COVID-19, interleukin-6, CRP, Cytokine, ferritin.

Introduction

SARS-CoV-2 infection causes fever, fatigue, dry cough and, in severe cases, pneumonia, acute respiratory syndrome and kidney failure. In some cases, SARS-CoV-2 infection can be fatal, with approximately 80% of patients having a mild and asymptomatic infection [12]. A significant part of the deaths caused by this disease occurred in the elderly and those suffering from co-morbidities [9]. One of the questions that interested the researchers was to determine whether it is possible to protect against this virus with a strong immune system. Because immunity is a defense mechanism that protects the stability of the internal environment of a person [6]. C-reactive protein (CRP) is a non-specific acute phase reagent during infections or inflammation. A higher level indicates a more severe infection and is considered an indicator of the severity of the disease. However, evidence that CRP is a prognostic indicator remains to be established [2]. A CRP threshold of 40 mg/L is suitable for predicting death [8]. Serum immunological biomarkers such as IL-6 and ferritin have been reported to be significantly increased in non-survivors and critically ill patients compared to survivors [5]. During acute lung injury and CRDS, a significant increase in inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 is associated with a "cytokine storm" and causes further tissue damage [7]. Ferritin and CRP are used as initial markers in the detection of inflammatory reactions. The increase of these substances in inflammatory reactions leads to an increase in the number of cytokines. These are the main biomarkers used in clinical and laboratory settings to predict mortality and severity of COVID-19 infection. Neutrophils, lymphopenia (decreased levels of lymphocytes in white blood

cells), and dramatic changes in the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) can be used to predict the severity of a COVID-19 infection. This study aims to evaluate the relationship of leukocytes, CRP, and ferritin with the severity of COVID-19 in patients with a positive PCR test for COVID-19.

Material and methods

Investigations In 2021-2022, investigations were conducted at the New Clinic specializing in Covid-19 patients. Also, the electronic medical data of the Central Nefchilar Hospital and Reference Clinic were used.

The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) analysis was taken from suspected patients referred to the laboratory. Necessary information, such as drug use and underlying diseases, was also recorded. A nasopharyngeal sample was collected for PCR. A blood sample was also taken from the cubital vein. Anti-preservative tubes were used for testing in all tests. After the formation of a clot, the samples were centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 15 minutes; the serum samples were separated and sent to the biochemistry department. Blood for CBC testing was collected in EDTA K2 anticoagulant tubes. After daily testing, patients' sera are stored at -20 C for one week. Cobas 6000 device, Sysmex XN 1000 Hematology inurement, and real-time PCR Roche was used for testing. The Medical Laboratory Group analyzed nasopharyngeal swabs and venous blood samples.

The authors collected data from the medical laboratory backup system and patient questionnaires according to a standard protocol. The diagnosis was made by real-time RT-PCR testing of nasal and pharyngeal swab samples according to the guidelines of the World

Health Organization [5]. At this stage, 236 women and 364 men entered the test. We considered patient demographic characteristics, including age, gender, co-morbidities (hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular), respiratory disease, blood group, clinical symptoms, including fever, and respiratory and digestive symptoms. Data were analyzed regarding various variables such as age, leukocyte parameters, neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), CRP and ferritin tests.

Determination of sample size for research activities provided by Cochrane ($d=0.05$). Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25 (SPSS Inc.,

Chicago, IL, USA) was used for data analysis. An independent t-test was performed for inferential statistical methods. The level of significance was considered as $P\text{-value}<0.05$ in all analyses.

Results

The average age in women was 52.3 and in men 52.8. Patient's symptoms were determined at the time of admission, and it was found that the most common symptoms were fatigue (81%), cough (63%), fever (57%), chest tightness, or shortness of breath (32.7%). 35.7% of patients complained of gastrointestinal symptoms, including nausea, diarrhea, loss of appetite, abdominal pain, and vomiting.

Table 1

Patient symptoms, biochemical serum tests, and leukocyte parameters in patients with COVID-19

Parameters	Female (n=236) Median (SD) COVID19 (+)	P-value	Male (n=364) Median (SD) COVID19(+)	P-value
Analysis of leukocytes				
WBC (1000/ μ L)	5.65(3.73)	1	4.94(3.42)	0.51
RBC	4.73(0.53)	0.63	4.94(0.88)	0.00
Lymphocyte (109 / L)	1.42(0.82)	1	1.39(1.56)	0.81
Neutrophil (109 / L)	3.56(3.84)	1	3.61(2.83)	1.00
PLT	237(105.34)	0.99	216(90.49)	0.77
Acute protein phase				
PCT	0.20(0.10)	0.00	0.23(0.10)	0.00
CRP (mg/L)	6.50(9.24)	0.64	15.56(32.45)	0.46
Ferritin (ng/mL)	230.9(154.75)	0.98	227.95(175.14)	0.94
IL-6	8.20(14.37)	0.29	8.50(13.63)	0.51
ESR	20(22)	0.00	24(20.61)	0.00

Regarding the laboratory results, 189 patients (31.90%) had CRP values greater than five mg/l. These 189 people had signs of pulmonary involvement and respiratory distress. Analysis of patients' serum ferritin showed that 312 patients (52.10%) had higher than normal ferritin. This study shows abnormality of IL-6, Neutrophil, Lymphocyte, ferritin, CRP, and RBC parameters in COVID-19 patients (Table 1).

Table 2

Mann-Whitney *U* test analysis of inflammatory markers by gender and age

	AGE		GENDER	
	Mann-Whitney U	P-value	Mann-Whitney U	P-value
WBC (1000/μL)	2885.5	0.136	39678.5	0.114
RBC	2181	0.001	33234.5	0.000
Lymphocyte (109 / L)	2288	0.002	41046	0.358
Neutrophil (109 / L)	2387	0.005	40862	0.314
PLT	2981.5	0.215	37279	0.006
CRP (mg/L)	3199.5	0.502	39135.5	0.066
Ferritin (ng/mL)	3007	0.241	41526	0.492
IL-6	2541	0.017	41874	0.603
ESR	3375	0.831	42226	0.726

According to the Mann-Whitney *U* test, PCT, PLT, and RBC variables were significantly different at 99% P-value, and PCT, Lymphocyte, Erythrocyte

sedimentation rate, and Interleukin-6 variables were significantly different at 99% P-value when compared by age. (Table 2).

Figure 1. Abnormality percentage of RBC, Neutrophil, Lymphocyte, ferritin, and CRP parameters in patients with COVID-19 in this study.

It was found that the number of Ferritin, lymphocytes, and IL-6 in patients changed more than other parameters. Also, according to the diagram, ferrite has the least change (figure 1).

Discussion

In our study, only 52.10% of patients had ferritin levels higher than the normal reference range. In studies of ferritin levels in COVID-19 patients, only patients with an acute condition had very high ferritin levels. In a study of twenty COVID-19 patients, individuals with severe and very severe COVID-19 infections were found to have elevated serum ferritin levels [3]. Chen et al. analyzed the clinical characteristics of 99 patients and reported that serum ferritin levels were above the normal range in 63 [10]. CRP levels can be used to diagnose pneumonia initially. Elevated CRP levels have been observed in patients with severe pneumonia [4]. Our study results are consistent with recent publications showing that CRP level in patients is a sensitive and early indicator of the severity of COVID-19. As a result of the study, 31.9% of the patients had CRP levels above five mg/L, and respiratory disorders were observed in them. A positive correlation between CRP levels, lung lesions, and disease severity has been established [1, 4, and 11].

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TREATMENT OF PERIODONTITIS BY SPLINTING AND SELECTIVE GRINDING

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Abstract

An important link in the complex treatment of periodontal diseases is the selective grinding of teeth, aimed at eliminating increased occlusal loads and creating a stimulating, functional tension in the supporting tissues of the teeth in order to rehabilitate and prevent traumatic occlusion. Traumatic occlusion develops against the background of an intact periodontium as a result of the action of an occlusal load that is excessive in magnitude or unusual in direction. The load begins to exceed the tolerance of the tissues surrounding the tooth and turns into a traumatic factor. Combined traumatic occlusion occurs when an increased load is combined with periodontal disease.

Key words: periodontitis, selective grinding, splinting of teeth.

Compared with gingivitis, chronic generalized periodontitis at the organ level is characterized by the presence of persistent progressive morphological and functional changes, and at the level of the organism as a whole - by the formation of a locally chronic odontogenic focus [1]. Accordingly, the dentist faces qualitatively different tasks in the treatment of this disease: the need to eliminate the chronic odontogenic focus of infection and reconstruct the affected periodontium. It is possible to achieve positive results only with the use of complex treatment of the disease [2]. Given the nature of inflammatory and destructive changes in the periodontium, the general treatment, planned depending on the degree of organ damage, is aimed at:

- treatment and stabilization of the affected organ or system;
- normalization of the organism's reactivity;
- restorative treatment;
- Correction of inflammatory, metabolic, micro-circulatory disorders in periodontal tissues and increase of local resistance of these tissues.

A necessary link in solving this problem during local treatment is the selective grinding of optimal chewing surfaces by eliminating premature tooth contacts and ensuring unhindered movements of the lower jaw. Supracontacts are determined using carbon paper or clasp wax plates in the position of central, anterior and lateral occlusion, as well as during movement of the lower jaw. Preliminary grinding of teeth can be carried out during the period of exacerbation of periodontitis. It consists in shortening the teeth that have protruded

from the hole and eliminating significant irregularities of the teeth [3.4]. The final grinding of the teeth is carried out in several visits only after conservative treatment of periodontal diseases and before the surgical stage. The intervals between visits should be at least 10-14 days. If it is necessary to increase the interalveolar height or make a fixed splint, the final grinding of the teeth is carried out after these measures. We started grinding teeth by eliminating premature contacts in the position of central occlusion.

In the anterior section, the cutting edges of the lower incisors are often ground, in some cases both antagonists. Supracontacts on the lateral teeth are eliminated by grinding off the bumps or depressions (fissures) after analyzing the lateral movements of the lower jaw [5]. When studying anterior occlusion, supracontacts are eliminated depending on the nature of the closing of the incisors in the position of central occlusion. With point or linear contact, the cutting edges of the upper teeth are ground, with planar contact, both antagonists. With orthognathic bite, premature contacts in the position of lateral occlusion are eliminated by grinding the upper buccal and lower lingual tubercles [6]. The buccal slopes of the palatine tubercles of the upper teeth and the lingual slopes of the buccal tubercles of the lower teeth fix the interalveolar height. Therefore, during transversal movements, the jaws should not grind. Grinding the surface of the teeth during anterior and lateral movements of the jaw should ensure uniform contact of multiple interdental contacts